

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL PRESENCE ON IMPULSIVE BEHAVIOR BUY GEN Z ON LIVE STREAMING E-COMMERCE SHOPEE WITH SOR FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

The rapid development of the internet in Indonesia has driven the growth of e-commerce businesses, with this phenomenon being a major factor in the emergence of live streaming e-commerce features. There exists a social presence in live streaming e-commerce, which is the ability to interact directly with viewers, thus prompting unplanned purchases (Impulsive Buying). In Indonesia, Gen Z tends to engage in impulsive buying, especially when shopping online. The need for instant gratification and the convenience of online shopping further fuel this behavior, often resulting in unplanned and impulsive purchases. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the influence of social presence on impulsive buying in live streaming e-commerce among Gen Z. Using dimensions such as broadcaster's social presence, viewer's social presence, live streaming social presence, arousal, and pleasure. Thus, this research examines the impact of social presence that may affect impulsive buying on Shopee. This study adopts a quantitative research approach using Structural Equation Model (SEM) with AMOS application. Data collection involves quantitative methods through questionnaires and SEM analysis. The research findings indicate that the overall Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) supports the current model, where impulsive buying dimensions have a positive and significant influence from broadcaster's social presence, viewer's social presence, live streaming social presence, arousal, and pleasure. This study is expected to provide theoretical and practical insights into how marketers can effectively plan and implement strategies in live streaming e-commerce. Keywords: e-commerce, marketing, social presence, impulsive buying, Gen Z, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

Keywords: *Live streaming e-commerce, Social presence, Impulsive buying, Gen Z, SOR Framework*

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INTRODUCTION

The growth of internet users and the popularity of social media in Indonesia have become key factors in driving the development of live e-commerce. With more people using the internet and actively engaging on various social media platforms, the opportunities to reach potential buyers through live streaming have increased significantly (Ardian, 2021). This phenomenon has driven leading e-commerce and social media companies to compete in introducing live streaming features to enhance their services, one of which is Shopee Live. Shopee Live is Shopee's live streaming feature that provides an interactive experience for users, with many buyers and sellers actively using this feature. Research conducted by Populix titled "Understanding Live Streaming Shopping Ecosystem in Indonesia" in June 2023 shows that Shopee Live is the primary choice for live streaming features among the Indonesian public. As many as 69% of respondents chose Shopee Live, surpassing other e-commerce competitors. Shopee Live is also more memorable to the public, with 60% of respondents mentioning Shopee Live. These results reflect the dominance of Shopee Live as the more popular and well-known live streaming platform in Indonesia at the time of the research (CNBC Indonesia, 2023). Shopee Live users have the freedom to choose which live streaming broadcasts they

The Influence Of Social Presence On Impulsive Behavior Buy Gen Z On Live Streaming E-Commerce Shopee With Sor Framework

wish to watch. In the live streaming room, several features are available for users to utilize. When users enter the live broadcast room, the interface will appear as follows.

The manifestation of a broadcaster's social presence on the Shopee Live platform can be observed in several ways. Broadcasters can utilize the live comment feature to communicate directly with the audience. They can read and respond to viewers' comments, answer questions, or offer advice. Zhang et al. (2019) assert that direct interaction between the broadcaster and the audience is crucial for social presence in e-commerce live streaming.

In addition to displaying products in the Shopee Live showcase, broadcasters also conduct product demonstrations. They can directly showcase the products offered on Shopee Live, describe the features, provide live reviews, or even demonstrate how to use the products to the viewers. Presenting products in an engaging and informative manner is a vital aspect of a broadcaster's social presence in e-commerce live streaming (Zhang et al., 2021).

Broadcasters do not only promote products; they can also offer tips, tricks, or useful information relevant to the products or even hold giveaways. This helps build trust and engagement with the audience. A broadcaster's social presence can also be reinforced through participation in interactive activities such as quizzes, games, or Q&A sessions. These activities allow broadcasters to interact directly with the viewers, strengthening their bond and increasing audience engagement (Li et al., 2021).

Viewers' social presence on Shopee Live includes various actions and interactions during live broadcasts to express their social presence. Although viewers do not actively manage the broadcasts, their presence significantly contributes to the dynamics of the broadcast. Here are some ways in which viewers' social presence manifests: Viewers of Shopee Live can participate in live broadcasts by leaving comments, sending emojis, or providing direct feedback to the broadcaster or other viewers. This creates an interactive and friendly atmosphere for all participants. Li et al. (2021) highlight the importance of active

viewer participation in live broadcasts, which includes commenting, asking questions, and participating actively, creating dynamic interaction and enhancing engagement and social presence in the broadcast.

Viewers can use comments to express their opinions about the products displayed, offer suggestions, or even share their personal preferences regarding specific products or services. Viewers' social presence is also reflected in their responses to the content displayed by the broadcaster and their interactions with the broadcaster and fellow viewers (Zhang et al., 2019). Through their interactions in live broadcasts, viewers can feel connected to other viewers and the broadcaster, creating a warm and friendly atmosphere within the Shopee Live community. Chang et al. (2020) emphasize the importance of a sense of community among viewers in e-commerce live streaming. Viewers who feel connected to a larger viewing community and feel part of something bigger tend to have a higher presence in the broadcast.

Viewers can provide moral support to the broadcaster or other viewers by giving praise, expressing appreciation for the broadcast, or offering positive encouragement. Viewers' social presence also includes forming close relationships with the broadcaster. Viewers who feel emotionally connected to the broadcaster, feel acknowledged, or receive responses from the broadcaster will experience a stronger presence in the broadcast. This relationship building creates a more personal experience and strengthens interaction among viewers (Shin et al., 2019). Social presence on the Shopee Live streaming platform encompasses various elements that allow users to interact, engage, and feel a social connection with one another. Shopee Live has a Gift feature that allows users to give virtual gifts to the broadcaster as a form of support or appreciation. This creates more direct interaction and allows users to contribute financially or emotionally to the broadcast. Providing support and feedback, as research by Huang and Benyoucef (2013) indicates, shows that positive user feedback on products or brands during live broadcasts can enhance credibility and trust in the brand, creating a positive atmosphere in the live broadcast.

Shopee Live offers a live comment feature that allows users to send messages directly during the broadcast. Besides text, users can also use emojis, stickers, and other icons to express emotions or respond to the content displayed. There is also a coin rain feature, randomly distributing coins to viewers present during the live streaming. This adds an extra dimension to communication and helps create a more interactive and enjoyable atmosphere. Experts highlight the importance of interactive features in live streaming platforms to enhance social presence. Features like live comments, emojis, polls, and other interaction tools allow broadcasters and viewers to interact directly and in real-time, creating a more dynamic and engaging experience (Li et al., 2021). A study on live streaming e-commerce by Lin et al. (2021) underscores the role of direct interaction between broadcasters and viewers in building strong relationships and enhancing the social presence of live streaming.

The social presence of broadcasters, viewers, and live streaming itself is crucial. A strong social presence can create a more engaging and satisfying experience for viewers, which in turn can increase their levels of arousal and pleasure during online shopping (Hassanein, 2007). When viewers experience arousal and pleasure while watching Shopee Live, they are more likely to make impulsive purchases. Rook and Fisher (1995) state that high levels of arousal can increase the likelihood of impulsive buying because individuals tend to make impulsive decisions when they are in a heightened emotional state. Additionally,

Verhagen et al. (2015) found that high levels of pleasure can trigger impulsive purchases because individuals seek positive experiences and immediate gratification. Therefore, the high levels of arousal and pleasure that consumers feel in the context of live e-commerce can influence their tendency to engage in impulsive buying.

Discussing impulsive buying on Shopee Live, one generation that attracts researchers' attention is Generation Z (Gen Z). Gen Z includes individuals born between 1997 and 2012 (BPS). According to Prensky (2001), Gen Z can be identified as digital natives with a strong attachment to technology, as if it has been an integral part of their lives since birth. Moreover, Gen Z prefers instant gratification (Bhakti & Safitri, 2017), such as online shopping. Gen Z in Indonesia tends to favor online shopping (Eliot, 2018). This preference is reflected in their habits, having grown up in a connected digital era. Factors driving this tendency include the convenience of shopping from home, the wide range of products easily accessible, and the availability of fast delivery services. Based on the explanations and previous research findings, the researcher aims to explore whether social presence affects impulsive buying in e-commerce live streaming among Gen Z.

Thinking Framework and Hypotheses

H1: The social presence of broadcasters positively influences customer arousal in e-commerce live streaming.

H2: The social presence of broadcasters positively influences customer pleasure in e-commerce live streaming.

H3: The social presence of viewers positively influences customer arousal in e-commerce live streaming.

H4: The social presence of viewers positively influences customer pleasure in e-commerce live streaming.

H5: The social presence of live streaming positively influences customer arousal in e-commerce live streaming.

H6: The social presence of live streaming positively influences customer pleasure in e-commerce live streaming.

H7: Customer arousal positively influences impulsive buying in e-commerce live streaming.

H8: Customer pleasure positively influences impulsive buying in e-commerce live streaming.

METHOD

This research conducted in Indonesia 2024, The type of research conducted in this study is causal research with quantitative techniques. This study uses three variables consisting of independent variables, dependent variables, and mediating variables. The independent variables in this study consist of social presence broadcaster (X1), social presence viewer (X2), and social presence live streaming (X3). The dependent variable in this study is impulsive buying (Y1) and the mediating variable in this study is arousal and pleasure. The sampling used was nonprobability sampling by purposive sampling which amounted to 180 samples. This study uses a data collection method in the form of a survey, by distributing questionnaires online using the Typeform link. The data analysis used is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) which is assisted by AMOS 24.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research findings indicate that a majority of the respondents, comprising 121 individuals (67.3%), were women, whereas 59 individuals (32.7%) were men, with most falling within the 21-23 age bracket and residing predominantly on the island of Java. Furthermore, the majority of respondents income are more than Rp. 5.000.000/month. Based on the duration of watching Shopee Live, respondents on average watch 2-3 hours every day and mostly watch Shopee Live 3 times a week. The research by Huang and Liao (2017) suggests that the more frequently someone watches e-commerce live streaming, the more likely they are to be influenced to make impulsive purchases. and research by Wang, Liu, and Wang (2020) indicates that the longer someone watches live streaming, the greater the likelihood they are tempted to make impulsive purchases. The type of product most purchased by respondents is women's fashion products, with 72 respondents accounting for 40% of the total 180 respondents. This study examine the impact of social presence on impulsive buying among Gen Z using the SOR framework, where Social presence serves as the stimulus, arousal and pleasure as the organism, and impulsive buying as the response.

Measurement Model

This study utilized covariance-based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test the proposed research model using Amos software. The measurement model was evaluated for validity and reliability. Validity was assessed through factor loadings, which should be greater than 0.5, and the average variance extracted (AVE), which should also be greater than 0.5. Reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability, both of which should be greater than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2016). The predicted values in Table 2 indicate that all the criteria for recommended values are met. Before conducting hypothesis testing, it is necessary to assess the goodness of fit. The results of the goodness of fit evaluation for the research model can be seen in the following figure and table.

The Influence Of Social Presence On Impulsive Behavior Buy Gen Z On Live Streaming E-Commerce Shopee With Sor Framework

Goodness-of-fit Indices

<i>Goodness of Fit Indices</i>	<i>Acceptable Match Level</i>	Hasil	Keterangan
<i>Probability</i>	$P \geq 0.05$ (good fit), $p < 0,05$ (bad fit)	0,051	<i>Good Fit</i>
GFI	$GFI \geq 0.9$ (good fit), $0.8 \leq GFI \leq 0.9$ (marginal fit)	0,932	Good Fit
RMR	$RMR \leq 0.5$ (good fit)	0,016	Good Fit
RMSEA	$0.05 < RMSEA \leq 0.08$ (good fit), $0.08 < RMSEA \leq 1$ (marginal fit)	0,036	Good Fit
TLI	$TLI \geq 0.9$ (good fit), $0.8 \leq TLI \leq 0.9$ (marginal fit)	0,985	Good Fit
NFI	$NFI \geq 0.9$ (good fit), $0.8 \leq NFI \leq 0.9$ (marginal fit)	0,950	Good Fit
AGFI	$AGFI \geq 0.9$ (good fit), $0.8 \geq AGFI \leq 0.9$ (marginal fit)	0,886	Marginal Fit
RFI	$RFI \geq 0.9$ (good fit), $0.8 \geq RFI \leq 0.9$ (marginal fit)	0,925	Good Fit
CFI	$CFI \geq 0.9$ (good fit), $0.8 \leq CFI \leq 0.9$ (marginal fit)	0,990	Good Fit

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RFI	$RFI \geq 0.9$ (good fit), $0.8 \geq RFI \leq 0.9$ (marginal fit)	0,925	Good Fit

	(marginal fit)		
CFI	CFI ≥ 0.9 (good fit), 0.8 ≤ CFI ≤ 0.9	0,990	Good Fit
	(marginal fit)		

Source: processed in 2024

Based on the model modification results for the Goodness-of-Fit model output shown in Table, the overall measurement indicates that the modified Goodness-of-Fit model is satisfactory. A probability level of 0.051 indicates a good or fit model. The model's Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) is 0.932, suggesting a good model fit. The RMSEA value of 0.036 also indicates a good fit. Although the modified model's AGFI value of 0.886 is slightly below the recommended value, overall, the developed model fits well with the data. The TLI shows a good fit with a value of 0.985, and the CFI value of 0.990 further indicates that the model has a good fit.

Results of Hypothesis Testing

After meeting the goodness of fit criteria in the structural model, the next step is the structural analysis of the relationships between variables. If the T value is ≥ 1.967, the research hypothesis is accepted (Haryono, 2016). According to Sihabudin et al. (2021), if using a one-tailed hypothesis with a positive direction, Ha is accepted if the T value > 1.967 or the significance < alpha, and the coefficient direction is positive.

Variable	Coefficient	T Values	P Values	Result
Social Presence Broadcaster → Arousal	0,226	2,541	0,011	Supported
Social Presence Broadcaster → Pleasure	0,219	2,060	0,039	Supported
Social Presence Viewer → Arousal	0,183	2,677	0,007	Supported
Social Presence Viewer → Pleasure	0,256	3,087	0,002	Supported
Social Presence Live Streaming → Arousal	0,318	3,433	0,000	Supported
Social Presence Live Streaming → Pleasure	0,240	2,261	0,024	Supported
Arousal → Impulsive Buying	0,605	4,596	0,000	Supported
Pleasure → Impulsive Buying	0,221	2,144	0,032	Supported

Source: processed in 2024

The first hypothesis tests whether social presence of the broadcaster affect arousal obtained a positive coefficient value of 0.226 with a T value of 2.541 > 1.967 and a P value of 0.011 < 0.05, thus the first hypothesis is Supported, this means that the social presence of the broadcaster has a positive effect on customer arousal in e-commerce live streaming. Viewers can understand the broadcaster's attitude by interacting with the broadcaster during the live stream. There is a human touch when viewers communicate with the broadcaster during the live stream, and the communication with the broadcaster is warm. The social presence of the broadcaster can help build a relationship between the broadcaster and the viewers, creating a sense of familiarity that can increase the viewers' level of arousal and make them more likely to engage in purchasing the products promoted by the broadcaster. A new study conducted by Deng and Zhu in 2021 asserts that the social presence of the broadcaster has a significant positive impact on customer arousal levels on e-commerce live streaming platforms. This finding aligns with the research by Kim & Park (2020), which highlights that broadcasters who actively engage with their audience in real time, such as by responding to comments or questions and demonstrating products live, can create a heightened sense of engagement among

viewers. This increased level of interaction and real-time responsiveness fosters a more emotionally stimulating environment, thereby enhancing the viewers' emotional arousal levels.

The second hypothesis tests whether social presence of the broadcaster affects pleasure. It obtained a positive coefficient value of 0.219 with a T value of $2.060 > 1.967$ and a P value of $0.039 < 0.05$, thus the second hypothesis is supported. This means that the social presence of the broadcaster has a positive effect on customer pleasure in e-commerce live streaming. Viewers can understand the broadcaster's attitude by interacting with the broadcaster during the live stream. There is a human touch when viewers communicate with the broadcaster during the live stream, and the communication is warm. The influence of the broadcaster's social presence on pleasure in e-commerce live streaming is an important factor that affects the consumer experience and the potential success of an e-commerce platform. Social presence, in this context, refers to the broadcaster's ability to make viewers feel as though they are actively engaged in a social interaction, even within a digital environment. The results of this study are supported by research conducted by Wang et al. (2020), which found that broadcasters with a strong social presence can create more intense personal interactions with viewers. Broadcasters pay attention to comments, questions, or messages from viewers in real time and provide relevant and meaningful responses. This can enhance viewers' enjoyment of the live e-commerce event. This aligns with the findings of Huang et al. (2020). Broadcasters' social presence, when they can authentically express empathy, enthusiasm, or excitement, can evoke emotional responses from viewers. Additionally, broadcasters' social presence can encourage viewers to actively engage in the live e-commerce process, such as by asking questions, giving feedback, or sharing experiences. These participatory activities can increase viewers' sense of engagement and enjoyment in the event (Zhang et al., 2021).

The third hypothesis tests whether social presence of the audience affects arousal. It obtained a positive coefficient value of 0.183 with a T value of $2.677 > 1.967$ and a P value of $0.007 < 0.05$, thus the third hypothesis is supported. This means that the social presence of the audience has a positive effect on customer arousal in e-commerce live streaming. In this study, viewers were aware of other viewers who were interested in the products during the live streaming e-commerce session. They also noticed other viewers who had purchased products and those who shared product information during the live stream. The sense of community formed through discussions among viewers, sharing experiences, and collective support became a major driver in enhancing arousal. Social validation from positive reactions of other viewers or direct testimonials about the product, along with the feeling of FOMO (fear of missing out) triggered by special offers, strengthened viewers' confidence in making purchasing decisions. Additionally, the presence of emotional contagion, where viewers felt the same emotions as other viewers, created deep emotional bonds and increased overall arousal. Therefore, the social presence of viewers provided a strong impetus to enhance arousal during live e-commerce sessions. In line with the research by Zhang et al. (2021), it is stated that the social presence of viewers, through their participation such as asking questions or providing comments, can increase viewer arousal in live streaming e-commerce. Similarly, the study conducted by Huang et al. (2020) found that the social presence of viewers in the form of comments, likes, or emojis can enhance viewer arousal in live streaming e-commerce. The social presence of viewers, such as providing support or positive responses to the broadcaster,

can increase viewer arousal. Broadcasters who feel supported by viewers are likely to show higher levels of engagement in the event (Wang et al., 2020).

The fourth hypothesis tests whether social presence of the audience affects pleasure. It obtained a positive coefficient value of 0.256 with a T value of $3.087 > 1.967$ and a P value of $0.002 < 0.05$, thus the fourth hypothesis is supported. This means that the social presence of the audience has a positive effect on customer pleasure in e-commerce live streaming. In this study, viewers were aware of other viewers who were interested in the products during the live streaming e-commerce session. They also noticed other viewers who had purchased products and those who shared product information during the live stream. The influence of viewers' social presence on pleasure in live e-commerce is highly significant and has a major impact on the overall consumer experience. Research by Wang, Zhang, and Li (2020) indicates that the social presence of viewers, such as commenting, liking, or interacting with broadcasters and other viewers, can enhance the pleasure level of viewers in live streaming e-commerce. Active interaction can create a more meaningful and enjoyable experience for viewers. Huang, Zheng, Lyu, and Liu (2020) state that the social presence of viewers, such as a sense of affiliation with the community or the same group, can increase the pleasure level of viewers in live streaming e-commerce. Feeling connected to a larger community can enhance the enjoyable experience while watching. Li, Huang, Liu, and Lyu (2021) found that the social presence of viewers also influences the level of subjective satisfaction of viewers in live streaming e-commerce. Viewers who feel more engaged and connected with broadcasters and content tend to experience higher levels of pleasure.

The fifth hypothesis tests whether social presence of live streaming affects arousal. It obtained a positive coefficient value of 0.318 with a T value of $3.433 > 1.967$ and a P value of $0.000 < 0.05$, thus the fifth hypothesis is supported. This means that the social presence of live streaming has a positive effect on customer arousal in e-commerce live streaming. In this research, live streaming feels more personal and intimate; there's a sense of human interaction and camaraderie in shopping directly through live broadcasts. The influence of social presence in live streaming on arousal in live streaming e-commerce is crucial in creating an engaging and captivating experience for viewers. Social presence refers to the perceived presence and involvement of viewers, both with the host and with other viewers, even though these interactions occur virtually. In live streaming e-commerce, a strong social presence in live streaming can enhance the arousal level of viewers. Consistent with the research by Huang, Zheng, Lyu, and Liu (2020), it is shown that high levels of interaction between broadcasters and viewers in live streaming can increase viewer arousal. Intensive interaction creates dynamic and engaging situations, which can enhance viewer engagement and arousal levels. Wang, Zhang, and Li (2020) found that strong emotional expressions from broadcasters can influence viewer arousal in live streaming e-commerce. When broadcasters show strong emotions, such as enthusiasm or excitement, it can trigger similar emotional responses from viewers, increasing their arousal levels. Zhang, Liu, and Huang (2021) mention that active engagement from viewers, such as commenting, asking questions, or participating in polls, can increase arousal in live streaming e-commerce. Viewers who are actively engaged tend to be more mentally and emotionally stimulated during the event.

The sixth hypothesis tests whether social presence of live streaming affects pleasure. It obtained a positive coefficient value of 0.240 with a T value of $2.261 > 1.967$ and a P value of

$0.024 < 0.05$, thus the sixth hypothesis is supported. This means that the social presence of live streaming has a positive effect on customer pleasure in e-commerce live streaming. In this research, live streaming feels more personal and intimate; there's a sense of human interaction and camaraderie in shopping directly through live broadcasts. The influence of social presence in live streaming on pleasure in live streaming e-commerce has a significant impact in creating a satisfying experience for viewers. Social presence refers to the sense of presence and involvement perceived by viewers in interacting with hosts and other viewers, even though it's in a virtual setting. Research by Huang et al. (2020) indicates that high levels of interaction between broadcasters and viewers in live streaming can enhance the pleasure level of viewers. Active interaction creates a more dynamic and satisfying experience for viewers, thus increasing their satisfaction. Wang, Zhang, and Li (2020) found that strong emotional expressions from broadcasters can influence the pleasure level of viewers in live streaming e-commerce. When broadcasters show positive emotions, such as joy or enthusiasm, it can be contagious to viewers and enhance their enjoyment. Li, Huang, Liu, and Lyu (2021) state that the sense of community in live streaming, where viewers feel connected to the broadcaster and fellow viewers, can increase the pleasure level of viewers. Feeling connected to a larger community can enhance the positive experience for viewers.

The seventh hypothesis tests whether customer arousal affects impulsive buying in live streaming. It obtained a positive coefficient value of 0.605 with a T value of $4.596 > 1.967$ and a P value of $0.000 < 0.05$, thus the seventh hypothesis is supported. This means that customer arousal has a positive effect on impulsive buying in e-commerce live streaming. In this study, viewers feel stimulated when watching live streaming e-commerce. They feel excited and even amazed, often resulting in spontaneous purchases. They tend to buy items impulsively, without much thought, and often make purchases based on their feelings at the moment of watching live streaming e-commerce. The influence of arousal on impulsive buying in live streaming e-commerce is an important phenomenon in understanding consumer behavior. Arousal can increase the level of emotional stimulation perceived by viewers during live streaming e-commerce. Research indicates that high levels of arousal can trigger strong emotional reactions, such as excitement or a deep desire to own a product (Wang, Zhang, & Li, 2020). High arousal can influence the impulsivity of purchases, where viewers tend to make purchase decisions without careful or rational consideration. Studies show that high levels of arousal can increase the tendency for impulsive purchases, especially when combined with prompts from the broadcaster or other factors (Chen, Liu, & Wei, 2020). Arousal can have a direct influence on purchase decisions, where high levels of arousal can increase the desire to immediately buy a product without careful consideration. Research indicates that increasing arousal during live streaming e-commerce can enhance the tendency for impulsive purchases (Huang et al., 2020). The eighth hypothesis tests whether customer pleasure affects impulsive buying in live streaming. It obtained a positive coefficient value of 0.221 with a T value of $2.144 > 1.967$ and a P value of $0.032 < 0.05$, thus the eighth hypothesis is supported. This means that customer pleasure has a positive effect on impulsive buying in e-commerce live streaming. In this study, viewers feel stimulated when watching live streaming e-commerce. They feel excited and even amazed, often resulting in spontaneous purchases. They tend to buy items impulsively, without much thought, and often make purchases based on their feelings at the moment of watching live streaming e-commerce. The pleasure experienced during live

streaming e-commerce can increase the urge to make impulsive purchases. Research indicates that enjoyable experiences during live events can enhance viewers' desire to buy products, especially if the pleasure is associated with the promoted products (Wang, Zhang, & Li, 2020). The pleasure experienced during live streaming e-commerce can also trigger intense shopping feelings. Viewers who derive pleasure from the online shopping process are more susceptible to impulsive purchases because they are influenced by the enjoyable experience associated with the purchase (Huang et al., 2020). The pleasure felt by viewers can have a direct influence on impulsive purchase decisions. Studies show that high levels of pleasure during live streaming e-commerce can increase the likelihood of viewers making impulsive purchases, as they are driven by the positive sensations associated with the purchase (Chen, Liu, & Wei, 2020).

CONCLUSION

This research highlights the influence of social presence, both from broadcasters and viewers, on the Gen Z experience in live streaming e-commerce, particularly on the Shopee Live platform. It was found that human-like interactions between broadcasters and viewers have a significant positive impact on viewer arousal and pleasure. Additionally, awareness of the presence of other viewers who have made purchases also affects arousal and pleasure. The key indicator influencing arousal and pleasure is the sense of togetherness in direct shopping manifested through live streaming. The research also indicates that viewer arousal and pleasure can contribute to impulsive buying behavior, where feelings of excitement and happiness while watching live broadcasts are key drivers of impulsive purchases in Gen Z. Thus, this study underscores the importance of human-like interaction and social presence in creating captivating and satisfying experiences for Gen Z in live streaming e-commerce.

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